

Viscometric studies of cesium halides, $(C_4H_9)_4NBr$, $NaBr$ and $NaBPh_4$ in aqueous acetone at 298.15 K

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The viscosities of cesium halides (Cl^- , Br^- and I^-), $(C_4H_9)_4NBr$, $NaBr$ and $NaBPh_4$ have been measured in (0, 20, 40, 80) mass% aqueous acetone at 298.15 K. The viscosity B -coefficients have been calculated by using the Jones-Dole equation. The ionic B -coefficients have been determined using the reference electrolytes $NaBPh_4$, $NaBr$ and $(C_4H_9)_4NBr$.

Ion solvent interactions in aqueous, non aqueous and mixed solvents have been studied employing several physico-chemical methods. Such investigations in mixed solvents have been reported previously¹. The viscometric method is known to give valuable information regarding ion-solvent interactions. In continuation of our earlier study² where we reported the volumetric properties of these electrolytes, we now report the viscosities of CsX ($X = Cl^-$, Br^- and I^-), $(C_4H_9)_4NBr$, $NaBr$ and $NaBPh_4$ in (0, 20, 40, 60 and 80) mass% aqueous acetone at 298.15 K in the present communication.

Results and discussion

The viscosities of cesium halides, $(C_4H_9)_4NBr$, $NaBr$ and $NaBPh_4$ are analysed with the help of Jones-Dole³ equation

$$\eta_r = (\eta/\eta_0) = 1 + AC^{1/2} + BC \quad (1)$$

where η and η_0 are the viscosities of the solution and the solvent respectively and C is the molar concentration. A is the measure of long range Coulombic forces between ions, while B reflects the effect of ion-solvent interactions. The plots of $[(\eta/\eta_0) - 1]/C^{1/2}$ versus $C^{1/2}$ for all the electrolytes in the whole composition range of aqueous acetone are found to be straight lines with intercept equal to A , and slopes give the Jones-Dole viscosity B -coefficients. A representative plot for $CsCl$ in all solvent mixtures is shown in Fig. 1. The A and B -coefficients obtained with a computerized least square method are listed in Table 1. The viscosity B -coefficients are negative for aqueous $CsCl$, $CsBr$ and CsI solutions, suggesting structure breaking tendencies of these electrolytes in pure water. The B values in these systems in-

Fig. 1. Plots of $(\eta_r - 1)/C^{1/2}$ versus $C^{1/2}$ for $CsCl$ in (0-80) mass% acetone : (○) 0, (⊕) 20, (●) 40, (◐) 60, (⊗) 80%.

crease with the increase of acetone in the solvent mixtures, indicating that the solute-solvent interactions increase with the decrease in dielectric constant of the solvent system. The B values are in the order : $CsCl < CsBr < CsI$, which is in agreement with the intrinsic ionic volume order : $Cl^- < Br^- < I^-$. This means that as the molar volume of electrolyte increases, solute-solvent interaction increases.

To have a better understanding of ion-solvent interactions, it is necessary to split the viscosity B -coefficient into

Table 1. Parameters of Jones-Dole equation CsCl, CsBr, CsI, (C₄H₉)₄NBr, NaBr and NaBPh₄ along with correlation coefficient, γ , in acetone + water mixtures at 298.15 K

Electrolyte	Mass% Acetone	A	B	γ
CsCl	0	0.005	-0.050, -0.049 ^a	0.9999
	20	0.052	0.231	0.9999
	40	0.058	0.520	0.9999
	60	0.063	0.802	0.9999
	80	0.065	1.094	0.9999
CsBr	0	0.002	-0.085	0.9999
	20	0.005	0.228	0.9999
	40	0.016	0.425	0.9999
	60	0.022	0.678	0.9999
	80	0.025	0.935	0.9999
CsI	0	0.004	-0.124, -0.118 ^b	0.9999
	20	0.005	0.199	0.9999
	40	0.006	0.381	0.9999
	60	0.007	0.642	0.9999
	80	0.018	0.901	0.9999
(C ₄ H ₉) ₄ NBr	0	0.008	1.146, 1.148 ^b	0.9999
	20	0.006	1.089	0.9999
	40	0.004	1.032	0.9999
	60	0.003	0.974	0.9999
	80	0.001	0.917	0.9999
NaBr	0	0.007	0.054, 0.054 ^c	0.9999
	20	0.009	0.197	0.9999
	40	0.013	0.341	0.9999
	60	0.015	0.482	0.9999
	80	0.017	0.625	0.9999
NaBPh ₄	0	0.008	1.146, 1.148 ^c	0.9999
	20	0.006	1.089	0.9999
	40	0.004	1.032	0.9999
	60	0.003	0.974	0.9999
	80	0.001	0.917	0.9999

^aRef. 10, ^bRef. 11, ^cRef. 12.

the individual ionic B -coefficients. This has been done in the present study using the (C₄H₉)₄NBr, NaBr and NaBPh₄ as the reference electrolytes, assuming⁴

$$\begin{aligned} B(\text{BPh}_4^-) / B(\text{Bu}_4\text{N}^+) &= r^3(\text{BPh}_4^-) / r^3(\text{Bu}_4\text{N}^+) \\ &= (5.35/5.00)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$B(\text{Bu}_4\text{NBPh}_4) = B(\text{BPh}_4^-) + B(\text{Bu}_4\text{N}^+) \quad (2)$$

where r is the ionic radius. The solubility of Bu₄NBPh₄ is very low in aqueous acetone at room temperature, therefore the above method could not be employed. The ionic B -

coefficient is therefore obtained from the relation⁵

$$B(\text{Bu}_4\text{NBPh}_4) = B(\text{Bu}_4\text{NBr}) + B(\text{NaBPh}_4) - B(\text{NaBr}) \quad (3)$$

Therefore, the Jones-Dole viscosity B -coefficients were determined for Bu₄NBr, NaBPh₄ and NaBr and using the above eq. (3), the B -coefficient of Bu₄NBPh₄ was calculated and from the eq. (2) the B -coefficient of Bu₄N⁺ was calculated, which enabled to get the ionic B -coefficient of Br⁻, and hence ionic B -coefficient of all the other ions could be calculated. The ionic B -coefficients for all cations and anions are listed in Table 2. The small negative B values of cation and small positive values of halide (Cl⁻, Br⁻ and I⁻) ions in water are due to the breakdown of tetrahedral structure of water and formation of strongly structured solvated ions. As the acetone content in the solvent mixture increases, these B values of small ions increase. Small ions have values considerably high in acetone than those in water and can reasonably be ascribed to increased ion-solvent interactions through charge transfer phenomenon.

Table 2. Ionic B values in different acetone + water mixtures at 298.15 K

Mass% Acetone	Na ⁺	Cs ⁺	Cl ⁻	Br ⁻	I ⁻	BPh ₄ ⁻	Bu ₄ N ⁺
0	-0.056	-0.195	0.145	0.110	0.071	1.269	1.036
20	0.081	0.112	0.118	0.116	0.086	1.192	0.973
40	0.219	0.303	0.277	0.122	0.078	1.114	0.910
60	0.358	0.554	0.248	0.124	0.088	1.042	0.850
80	0.421	0.717	0.331	0.194	0.175	0.818	0.668

Experimental

Water was distilled in quick-fit apparatus over alkaline KMnO₄ and H₂SO₄. The electric conductance of distilled water varied between 7×10^{-7} to $9 \times 10^{-9} \Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$. Acetone was purified⁶ by refluxing with potassium permanganate for two hours. The solution was cooled and Na₂CO₃ was added to it. Two hours later, it was filtered and distilled. Distillate was further distilled and preserved over anhydrous calcium chloride in vacuum desiccator. The purity of acetone was checked by comparing its observed density (0.78442 g cm⁻³) with that of 0.7844 g cm⁻³ at 298.15 K reported in the literature⁷.

CsCl, CsBr and CsI used were of AnalaR grade, with purity greater than 99%, NaBPh₄ was from E. Merck with purity greater than 99.5%, NaBr was from Loba Chemie Indoaustral company with purity >99% and the (C₄H₉)₄NBr used was from Fluka Chemie, AG, ch-9470

Assay >98% (Br). All these electrolytes were vacuum dried and used without further purification. Acetone + water mixtures of compositions (0, 20, 40, 60 and 80) mass% acetone were prepared by mixing known masses of water and acetone in glass-stoppered flasks.

Accurately known masses of electrolytes were dissolved in particular solvent to give solutions of desired concentrations. Electrolyte concentrations varied from (0.005 to 0.05) *M*. Densities were determined by using 15 cm³ bicapillary pycnometer as described earlier⁸. The estimated accuracy of density measurements of solvent and electrolyte solutions was $\pm 0.00005 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$.

The dynamic viscosities were measured using an Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer⁹, calibrated with conductivity water. An electronic digital stop watch with readability of $\pm 0.01 \text{ s}$ was used for the flow time measurements. At least three repetitions of each data reproducible to $\pm 0.05 \text{ s}$ were obtained, and the results were averaged. Since all flow times were greater than 200 s and capillary radius (0.5 mm) was far less than its length (50–60 mm), the kinetic energy and end corrections, respectively, were found to be negligible. The values of dynamic viscosities are reproducible to $\pm 0.003 \text{ mPa.s}$.

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